

Knowledge Regarding Post-Operative Self Care Activities of Cataract Patients

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ABSTRACT

Eyes are same like a camera. If the lens in the camera gets scratches/abrasions then, pictures will be appeared blur. This condition is called cataract. If this condition is left untreated can lead to the opacity or clouding of the natural lens of eyes and further may lead to permanent loss of vision. Good eyesight is an essential part of the body for proper growth and development of the individual. The main aim of the study is to assess the knowledge of cataract patient regarding post operative self care activities. A quantitative descriptive survey study was conducted to assess the knowledge regarding post-operative self care activities of cataract patients and to find the association between knowledge score and demographic variables of the cataract patients. Total 155 study participants were selected by purposive sampling technique from Eye ward, Himalayan Hospital Dehradun, Uttarakhand. Data revealed that most 97 (62.5%) had moderately adequate level of knowledge, 31(20.1%) had inadequate and 27 (17.4%) had adequate level of knowledge regarding post operative self care activities. Domains were included "cleaning of eyes", "instillation of eye drop" and "post operative precautions" to assess the knowledge regarding self care. The result findings shown that the cataract patients had maximum 27.8% knowledge regarding post-operative precautions and only 7.6% regarding the instillation of eye drops. It was concluded that cataract patients had moderate knowledge regarding post-operative self care activities.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Post operative self care activities, Cataract patients

I. INTRODUCTION

Eyes are like a camera. If the lens in a camera has scratches, the pictures will appear blurred, we will see blurred images or nothing at all. Such a condition is called cataract where there is opacity or clouding of the eye's natural lens, which if not treated can lead to blindness. Good eyesight is essential for the proper development of all the facilities of the individual.

Cataract is very common in older people. There are, many causes for cataract; they are smoking, diabetes, deterioration in the nutrition of the lens, deposits of acids and salt between lens fibers and disintegrity of lens fibers, use of alcohol and prolonged exposure to sunlight.

1.1 Need of study:-

In the medical dictionary 'vision' is defined as the special sense by which the qualities of an object (as color, luminosity, shape, and size) constituting its appearance are perceived and which is mediated by the eye.

Cataract is the leading cause of blindness accounting for 55% blindness world wide .It is currently estimated that there are over 20 million people blind from cataract in the world and it is mostly prevalent in people over 50 years. World Health

Organization survey has shown that there is a backlog of over 22 million blindness in India and 80.1% blindness are due to cataract.

The annual incidence of cataract blindness is about 3.8 million in India and present prevalence is 0.56% in Uttarakhand.

1.2 Statement of problem:-

A Descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding post-operative self care activities of cataract patient in selected hospital Dehradun.

1.3 Objectives:-

- To assess the knowledge regarding post-operative self care activities of cataract patients.
- To find the association between knowledge score and demographic variables of the cataract patients.

1.4 Assumptions:-

- Patient will have some knowledge regarding self care after cataract surgery.
- Sample will be true representative of population.

1.5 Delimitation:-

- This study was delimited to post operative cataract patients of Himalayan hospital Dehradun, Uttarakhand.
- Single time data collection in cross-section study.
- One Setting only.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this study was non experimental descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted at Himalayan Hospital, Dehradun, Uttarakhand. The sample was 155 post-operative cataract patients were selected by using purposive sampling technique. The tool used for the study was Self Reported Structured Checklist section A Description of demographic characteristics of the study participants (demographic data such as Age, gender, educational status, occupation, family income in per month in Rs., Area of living, types of family, Any other co-morbidity with cataract) and section B (consisting of self reported structured checklist to assess the knowledge on i.e cleaning of the eye, Instillation of eye drops, Post-Operative care precautions) section C (Association between knowledge score and the demographic variables regarding post operative self care activities of cataract patients.)

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Related to Demographic Variable of Cataract Patients.

N=155

S. No.	Demographic Variable	(f)	(%)
1.	Age in years		
1.1	50-60	64	41.2
1.2	61-70	60	38.7
1.3	71-80	31	20.1
2.	Gender		
2.1	Male	80	51.6
2.2	Female	75	48.4
3.	Educational Status		
3.1	No formal education	101	65.2
3.2	Primary	39	25.0
3.3	Secondary	03	2.2
3.4	High secondary	10	6.4
3.5	Graduation and above	02	1.2
4.	Occupation		
4.1	Homemaker	75	48.4
4.2	Farmer	70	45.2
4.3	Retired	10	6.4
5.	Family Income per month in Rs.		
5.1	1000-5000	96	61.9
5.2	5001-11000	59	38.1
6.	Area of Living		
6.1	Rural	112	72.3
6.2	Urban	24	15.5
6.3	Semi Urban	19	12.2
7.	Types of family		
7.1	Nuclear	84	54.2
7.2	Joint family	70	45.2
7.3	Extended family	01	0.6
8.	Any Other co-morbidity with cataract		
8.1	Yes	40	25.8
8.2	No	115	74.2
8.1	If specify than specify		
	Hypertension	28	18.0
	Diabetes Mellitus	12	7.74
	Hyperthyroidism	00	00
	Others	00	00

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO.3.1

The demographic characteristics revealed that 41.2 % of the subjects were in the age group of 50-60 years. Half of subjects 51.6 % were male, majority of the subjects 72.3 % belonged to rural area, More than half of the subjects 54.2% belonged to nuclear family, majority of the subjects 74.2 % were not having any other co-morbidity with cataract.

3.2 Scoring of knowledge level of cataract patients regarding post-operative self care activities.

N=155

S. No	Level of knowledge	Max. Score	(f)	(%)
1.	Inadequate	5-8	31	20.1
2.	Moderately adequate	9-13	97	62.5
3.	Adequate	14-17	27	17.4

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO.3.2

Data showed that level of knowledge of cataract patient about post operative self care activities. Most 97 (62.5%) had moderately adequate level of knowledge, 31(20.1%) had inadequate and 27 (17.4%) had adequate level of knowledge.

3.3 Related to Association between knowledge score and the demographic variables regarding post operative self care activities of cataract patients.

N=155

S. No	Demographic Variable	Below median (11)	At and above median (11)	χ^2
1.	Age in years			
1.1	50-60	47	51	1.139
1.2	66-80	22	35	
2.	Gender			
2.1	Male	37	43	0.036
2.2	Female	34	41	
3.	Educational Status			
3.1	No Formal Education, primary education	63	75	0.146
3.2	High secondary ,Graduation and above	7	10	
4.	Occupation			
4.1	Homemaker	36	39	0.151
4.2	Farmer, Retired	35	45	
5.	Family Income in per month in Rs.			
5.1	1000-5000	38	58	1.764
5.2	5001-11000	30	29	
6.	Area of living			
6.1	Rural	55	57	0.743
6.2	Urban, semi urban	21	22	
7.	Types of family			
7.1	Nuclear	32	52	1.330
7.2	Joint family, Extended family	31	40	
8.	Any other co-morbidity with cataract			
8.1	Yes	19	21	0.243
8.2	No	49	66	

DESCRIPTION OF TABLE NO.3.3

This table shows that there was no significant association between knowledge score and demographic variables such as Age, Gender, Education Status, Occupation, Family Income, Area of Living, types of family, any other disease condition with cataract.

IV. NURSING IMPLICATIONS

1. Nurses are supportive and educative while caring for the patients.
2. Nurses not only do the assessment, but must make sure whether patients really understood the importance of self care, follow up visits, and the complications that may arise after discharge.
3. Nurses working in the eye ward can educate the patient about self care after cataract surgery in pre operative phase. The nurse administrator can train the nurses to give identify teaching regarding post operative self care activities.
4. Nurse Administrator can prepare written policies and protocol regarding post operative care of cataract patient.
5. The nursing students can conduct many studies in different ways to bring out the newer perspective in nursing care and educate patients.

V. CONCLUSION

Study concluded that cataract patient did not have adequate knowledge regarding post operative self care activities. Thus, nurses must take action to educate the patients on continuous basis regarding self care and prevention of complications after cataract surgery.

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